

Determinants of Students' Decision to Choose the Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University, Medan

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ABSTRACT

Education is a factor that plays a role in all sectors. The decision to vote by the student is influenced by the marketing mix strategy of the service which consists of: product, price, people, location, process, physical evidence. The problem in this research is to know how far marketing service mix strategy that consist of: product, price, people, location, process, physical evidence to decision of student choosing and how far influence of reference group to decision of student choose. The purpose of this study was to determine whether the marketing mix of services and reference groups had an effect on the decision of the students to have the choice. The approach in this study is quantitatively supported by the survey, explanatory explaining the causal relationship between the variables affecting the hypothesis and measured by Likert scale Data collection methods using questionnaires with the number of respondents as many as 100 students of the Faculty of Economics and Business. Analysis method used in this research is Descriptive Statistic Data Analysis and Multiple Linear Regression Analysis. The result of this research shows that product, price, people, process, physical evidence have positive and significant influence to student decision in choosing, but location, process and reference group have positive and insignificant effect to student decision. The conclusion of this research is marketing service mix strategy which consists of product, price, person, process, location, physical evidence, and reference group influence to student decision to choose Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University Medan.

Keywords: *Service Marketing Mix and Decision Making*

INTRODUCTION

Education is a supporting factor that plays an important role today. Humans need education in their lives. Education is an effort so that humans can develop their potential through learning processes and / or other ways known and recognized by the community. Education has an important role in improving the quality of human resources. Education is a form of long-term investment (long-term investment) which means that the investment in the field of human resources can not be immediately enjoyed by the results, but in the long term it is believed that the benefits will soon be felt preparing quality human resources

through quality education channels, therefore all the pillars of the nation's strength must make as much investment as possible to improve the quality (process and results of the world of education).

PTN is still a favorite for students who want to continue their education to Higher Education. This can be seen from the large number of students applying to PTN. Therefore, each PTS must do a special strategy and promotion that is different from other PTS. The size for obtaining students depends on the delivery of the PTS in question, which is clearly seen from the service marketing mix strategy applied by PTS. In addition to the service marketing

mix strategy, accreditation status also affects the decision of prospective students to choose PTS as a place to continue their studies. Besides the increasing competition, another problem faced by universities is the increasingly critical students in making decisions to choose a college. According to Kotler and Keller (2016) buying decisions, namely: "Several stages carried out by consumers before making a product purchase decision". Kotler also mentioned that "the specific purchasing process consists of the following sequence of events: introduction to the problem of needs, information seeking, evaluation of alternatives, purchasing decisions and post-purchase behavior". The conclusion is that buying decisions are a series of cognitive processes carried out by someone to arrive at the choice of the product to be bought so that it will encourage someone to buy a product.

In this study there are several determinant factors that influence purchases, namely; Service marketing mix and reference group. Kotler and Keller (2016) state that the marketing mix is a tactical series that can be controlled by: products, prices, places, promotions, processes, people and physical evidence that is integrated by the company to produce responses desired by companies in the target market. Every company uses a number of tools to get consumer responses to marketing activities carried out by the company. One of the tools used by companies in compiling marketing strategies by using the marketing mix. According to Tjiptono (2012) "the service marketing mix is a set of tools that marketers can use to shape the characteristics of services offered to customers". Kotler and Armstrong (2012) state that in the marketing mix there is a set

of marketing tools known as 4P marketing mix, namely product (product), price (price), place or distribution channel (place), and promotion (promotion), while in marketing services have several additional marketing tools such as people (people), physical evidence (physical evidence), and process (process), so that it is known as a 7P marketing mix. In this study, not all marketing mix elements of services are examined, but only six elements, namely: product, price, people, location, process, physical evidence. The promotion element is not examined in this study because the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan Medan University is a favorite faculty, the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University Medan is not too intense in its promotion, and better known through relatives, friends and family who have studied at the Faculty Economics and Business, Harapan University Medan. Therefore in this study, researchers included reference groups as variables outside the service marketing mix. Purchasing decisions are also influenced by reference groups. According to Burhan (2010), the Reference Group (Reference Group) or Reference Group is a group of people who significantly influence a person's behavior. In marketing perspectives the reference group is a group that serves as a reference for someone in consumption purchasing decisions. Harapan University in Medan has several faculties, including: Faculty of Economics and Business, Faculty of Engineering and Faculty of Foreign Languages. Campus 1 is located at Imam Bonjol No. 38 Medan while Campus 2 is located on HM. Jhoni. Of the three Faculties at the Harapan University Medan. The Faculty of Economics and Business is the most popular faculty for prospective students.

Table 1 Number of Students of the Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University Medan Academic Year 2012-2016

No.	Study program	2012/ 2013	2013/ 2014	2014/ 2015	2015/ 2016	2016/ 2017	Total
1	S.1 Accounting.	274	234	246	161	107	1022
2	S.1 Management	307	223	210	118	166	1024
	Total	581	457	456	279	273	2046

Source: Academic of the Faculty of Economics, Harapan University, Medan

From Table 1.1 it can be seen the phenomenon of the decline in the number of students from 2012-2017. For this reason, the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University Medan, as a favorite faculty, seeks to focus more on its marketing mix strategy so that students prefer the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.

The marketing mix service has a strong influence on the success of a company or college. In understanding the marketing of higher education services, the strategy applied is inseparable from the marketing mix strategy. The marketing mix strategy in the relationship of high education services marketing can not be separated from the product, price, people, location, process, physical evidence, and reference groups.

The product is a unified learning plan as a guideline for the implementation of academic and professional education. The product used in this study is the Study Program. The Study Program is organized on the basis of a curriculum that is intended so that students can master the knowledge, attitudes, and behaviors / skills that are in accordance with their intended goals. Tjiptono (2014) states that price is a monetary unit or other measure including other goods and services that are exchanged in order to obtain ownership rights or users of goods and services. Prices in this case are registration fees, annual tuition fees that can be paid in installments, and exam fees.

According to Kotler and Keller (2016), that "place (distribution) includes the activities of companies to provide products for target consumers". According to Yazid (2001), that "process is all actual procedures, mechanisms and activity flows where services are delivered which is a service system or operation". The process carried out by the Faculty of Economics, Harapan University Medan starts with: registration, testing, re-registration, and lectures.

People are actors who have an important role during the service delivery

process and can influence consumers' perceptions to buy and use these social products. In this case the person in question is Educational Staff (Lecturer), management, and staff staff.

Physical evidence is a supporting factor in determining the decisions of prospective students in choosing the universities they enter. Among them are processes that start from visits to see buildings, lecture halls, libraries, computer laboratories and humans where services are delivered, where companies and consumers interact and each component of tangible facilitates the appearance or communication of these services. The Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University Medan has a nice building and a comfortable room.

According to Burhan (2010) Definition of Reference Groups Reference Group (Reference Group) or Reference Group is an individual or group of people that significantly affects a person's behavior. Harapan Medan is better known by many people, so the reference group has an influence on someone's behavior in choosing the Faculty of Economics, Harapan University of Medan.

Hypothesis

Based on the formulation of the problem, the hypotheses of this study are:

1. Products have a positive and significant effect on student decisions to choose the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.
2. Prices have a significant positive effect and on student decisions to choose the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.
3. Location has a positive and significant effect on students' decision to choose the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.
4. People have a positive and significant influence on students' decisions to choose the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.
5. The process has a positive and significant effect on student decisions to

- choose the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.
6. Physical Evidence has a positive and significant effect on the student's decision to choose the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.
 7. Reference Groups have a significant positive effect on student decisions choosing the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.
 8. Products, prices, promotions, locations, people, processes, social classes, and groups have a positive and significant effect simultaneously on student decisions to choose the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Method of Collecting Data

The type of research used in this study is explanatory with a quantitative approach. The explanatory research according to Sugiyono (2012) is a study that explains the causal relationship between variables that influence the hypothesis. In this study there are at least two variables that are connected and this study serves to explain, predict and control a symptom.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 Description of Respondent's Answers on Product Variables.

No	Statement	Respondent's answer										Max	Min	Modus	Mean	Conclusion
		SS		S		KS		TS		STS						
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%					
1	The Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University Medan has a study program that is in great demand	29	29	28	28	30	30	3	3	0	0	5	2	4	3.93	Agree
2	The Faculty of Economics, Harapan University Medan has accreditation B	28	28	39	39	29	29	4	4	0	0	5	2	4	3.91	Agree
3	The Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University Medan has facilities that support lecture activities	28	28	38	38	31	31	3	3	0	0	5	2	4	3.91	Agree
Product Score															3.92	WELL
Average Score		1,00 – 1,80 = Strongly Disagree; 1,81 – 2,60 = Disagree; 2,61 – 3,40= Less Agree; 3,41 – 4,20 = Agree; 4,21 – 5,00 = Strongly agree														

Source: Research results, 2017 (data processed)

Associative research methods according to Sugiyono (2012) are "associative research is research that aims to determine the influence or relationship between two or more variables.

According to Sugiyono (2011), the population is a generalization area consisting of: objects / subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics set by researchers to be studied and then conclusions drawn. While according to Sujarweni (2014) states that, population is a generalization region consisting of object / subject that has certain qualities and characteristics set by the researcher to be studied and then drawn conclusions. The populations in this study are all students of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University of Medan, total 2046 people. The types of data collected in this study are sourced from:

1. Primary data is data obtained by conducting interviews (interviews) and the distribution of questionnaires (questionnaires) to research respondents.
2. Secondary data, namely data originating from journals, documents, and regulations in the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University Medan, which supports research.

Based on the average frequency of respondents' answers in Table 4.2, it can be seen that the average value of the respondent's answer for the product variable is 3.91 indicating that the product variable is considered good by students.

Table 3 Respondent's Answer Description on Price Variables

No	Statement	Respondent's answer										Max	Min	Modus	Mean	Conclusion
		SS		S		KS		TS		STS						
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%					
1	Registration and Development Money at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University of Medan in accordance with existing building facilities	28	28	38	38	31	31	3	3	0	0	5	2	4	3.92	Agree
2	Tuition at the Faculty of Business Economics, Harapan University of Medan can be paid twice	28	28	38	38	31	31	3	3	0	0	5	2	4	3.91	Agree
3	The exam money at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University of Medan is not too expensive	28	28	37	37	31	31	4	4	0	0	5	2	4	3.91	Agree
Price Score															3.92	WELL
Average Score		1,00 – 1,80 = Strongly Disagree; 1,81 – 2,60 = Disagree; 2,61 – 3,40= Less Agree; 3,41 – 4,20 = Agree; 4,21 – 5,00 = Strongly agree														

Source: Research results, 2017 (data processed)

Based on the average frequency of respondents' answers in Table 4.3 it can be seen that the average value of the respondent's answer for the product variable is 3.92 indicating that the price variable has been considered good by students.

Table 4 Description of Respondents' Answers to Location Variables

No	Statement	Respondent's answer										Max	Min	Modus	Mean	Conclusion
		SS		S		KS		TS		STS						
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%					
1	The location of the Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University Medan is easy to reach	36	36	37	37	22	22	5	5	0	0	5	2	4	4.04	Agree
2	Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University Medan is close to the city center	42	42	32	32	15	15	7	7	4	4	5	1	4	4.01	Agree
Location Score															4.025	WELL
Average Score		1,00 – 1,80 = Strongly Disagree; 1,81 – 2,60 = Disagree; 2,61 – 3,40= Less Agree; 3,41 – 4,20 = Agree; 4,21 – 5,00 = Strongly agree														

Source: Research results, 2017 (data processed)

Based on the average frequency of respondents' answers in Table 4.4, it can be seen that the average value of respondents' answers to the location variable is 4.25 indicating that the location variable has been considered good by students.

Table 5 Description of Respondents' Answers on People's Variables

No	Statement	Respondent's answer										Max	Min	Modus	Mean	Conclusion
		SS		S		KS		TS		STS						
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%					
1	The Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University Medan has the qualifications of competent educative staff	28	28	38	38	31	31	3	3	0	0	5	2	4	3.91	Agree
2	The Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University Medan has administrative staff and friendly employees	28	28	38	38	31	31	3	3	0	0	5	2	4	3.91	Agree
3	The Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan Medan has good management, making it easier for me in matters related to lectures	28	28	38	38	31	31	3	3	0	0	5	2	4	3.89	Agree
People Score															3.9	WELL
Average Score		1,00 – 1,80 = Strongly Disagree; 1,81 – 2,60 = Disagree; 2,61 – 3,40= Less Agree; 3,41 – 4,20 = Agree; 4,21 – 5,00 = Strongly agree														

Source: Research results, 2017 (data processed)

Based on the average frequency of respondents' answers in Table 4.5, it can be seen that the average value of the respondents' answers for the person variable is 3.9, indicating that the variable of the person has been considered good by the student.

Table 6 Description of Respondents' Answers to Process Variables

No	Statement	Respondent's answer										Max	Min	Modus	Mean	Conclusion
		SS		S		KS		TS		STS						
		F	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%					
1	The procedure for admitting students at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University Medan is not complicated	31	31	35	35	33	33	1	1	0	0	5	2	4	3.96	Agree
2	The lecture process at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University Medan is not boring	26	26	36	36	36	36	2	2	0	0	5	2	3	3.86	Agree
Process Score															3.91	WELL
Average Score		1,00 – 1,80 = Strongly Disagree; 1,81 – 2,60 = Disagree; 2,61 – 3,40= Less Agree; 3,41 – 4,20 = Agree; 4,21 – 5,00 = Strongly agree														

Source: Research results, 2017 (data processed)

Based on the average frequency of respondents' answers in Table 4.6, it can be seen that the average value of the respondent's answer to the process variable is 3.91 indicating that the process variable has been deemed good by students.

Based on the average frequency of respondents' answers in Table 4.7, it can be seen that the average value of the respondent's answer to the physical evidence variable is 3.83 indicating that the physical evidence variable has been considered good by students.

Table 7 Respondent's Answer Description on Physical Evidence Variables

No	Statement	Respondent's answer										Max	Min	Modus	Mean	Conclusion
		SS		S		KS		TS		STS						
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%					
1	The appearance of lecturers and employees in the Faculty and Business Economics of Harapan University Medan is very polite	29	29	34	34	22	22	15	15	0	0	5	2	4	3.77	Agree
2	The room at the Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University Medan is very comfortable	26	26	39	39	32	32	3	3	0	0	5	2	4	3.88	Agree
Physical Evidence Score															3.83	WELL
Average Score		1,00 – 1,80 = Strongly Disagree; 1,81 – 2,60 = Disagree; 2,61 – 3,40= Less Agree; 3,41 – 4,20 = Agree; 4,21 – 5,00 = Strongly agree														

Source: Research results, 2017 (data processed)

Table 8 Description of Respondents' Answers on the Reference Group Variables

No	Statement	Respondent's answer										Max	Min	Modus	Mean	Conclusion
		SS		S		KS		TS		STS						
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%					
1	I chose the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, because my family members had studied at the Faculty of Economics, Harapan University, Medan	39	39	8	8	51	51	2	2	0	0	5	2	3	3.84	Agree
2	I chose the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University Medan, because I followed friends	42	42	7	7	49	49	2	2	0	0	5	2	3	3.89	Agree
3	I chose the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan, because of the completion of a number of my relatives	34	34	37	37	24	24	5	5	0	0	5	2	4	4.00	Agree
Reference Group Score															3.87	WELL
Average Score		1,00 – 1,80 = Strongly Disagree; 1,81 – 2,60 = Disagree; 2,61 – 3,40= Less Agree; 3,41 – 4,20 = Agree; 4,21 – 5,00 = Strongly agree														

Source: Research results, 2017 (data processed)

Based on the average frequency of respondents' answers in Table 4.8, it can be seen that the average value of the respondent's answer for the reference group variable is 3.87 indicating that the reference group variable has been considered good by students.

RESULT

Normality Test

Data normality test is very important in parametric statistical analysis so that the regression model is free from prediction

errors. The SPSS Test results for normality of data can be seen as follows:

Table 9 Normality Test with Kolmogorov-Smirnov One-Sample

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N		100
Normal Parameters ^a	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1.01546796
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.271
	Positive	.134
	Negative	-.271
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		3.709
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.067
a. Test distribution is Normal.		

Source: Research results, 2017 (data processed)

From the results of data processing in Table 4.13 above, it can be seen that the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) significance value is 0.067, it can be concluded that the variable data are normally distributed because of significance > 0.05.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity test aims to examine the variance of residual variance in a period of observation to another period. Heteroscedasticity analysis uses a scatterplot graph test. It can be seen in the following picture:

From the picture of the scatterplot above, it can be seen that the points spread randomly and did not form a specific or irregular pattern. This indicates there is no heteroscedasticity in the regression model so that the regression model is feasible to use.

Multicollinearity Test

The results of the multicollinearity test can be seen in the following table:

Table 10 Multicollinearity Test Results

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	Product	.150	6.686
	Price	.231	4.338
	Location	.507	1.974
	Person	.190	5.252
	Process	.347	2.880
	Physical Evidence	.200	4.999
	Reference Group	.530	1.888

Source: Research results, 2017 (data processed)

From the results of the above test, it can be seen that the tolerance numbers of all independent variables > 0.1 and VIF < 10. This indicates that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables in the regression model in this study.

Analysis of Multiple Linear Regression

Table 11 Regression Test Results

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.894	.761		1.175	.243
	Product	.232	.116	.234	1.995	.049
	Price	.215	.093	.218	2.314	.023
	Location	.073	.086	.054	.848	.399
	Person	.263	.103	.266	2.560	.012
	Process	.090	.116	.060	.778	.438
	Physical Evidence	.276	.134	.208	2.057	.043
	Reference Group	.026	.060	.027	.433	.666

Source: Attachment to SPSS Output

Based on Table 4.9 the results of testing the hypothesis of the Product influence on the decision to choose obtained a significance value of 0.004 (Sig. < 0.05) then H₀ is rejected. This means that the product has a significant effect on the decision to choose the students of the Faculty of Economics and Business in the Harapan University Medan environment.

Product Influence on Choosing Decisions

Based on Table 4.9 the results of testing the hypothesis of the Product influence on the decision to choose obtained a significance value of 0.004 (Sig. < 0.05) then H₀ is rejected. This means that the product has a significant effect on the decision to choose the students of the Faculty of Economics and Business in the Harapan University Medan environment.

Influence of Prices on Decisions to Choose

Based on Table 4.9 the results of testing the hypothesis of the effect of price on the decision to choose obtained a significance value of 0.002 (Sig. <0.05) then H0 is rejected. This means that the price has a significant effect on the decision to choose the students of the Faculty of Economics and Business in the Harapan University Medan environment.

Effect of Location on Decision to Choose

Based on Table 4.9 the results of testing the hypothesis of the influence of location on the decision to choose obtained a significance value of 0.004 (Sig. <0.05) then H0 is rejected. This means that the location has a significant effect on the decision to choose the students of the Faculty of Economics and Business in the Harapan University Medan environment.

The Effect of People on Decisions to Choose

Based on Table 4.9 the results of testing the hypothesis of the influence of people on the decision to choose obtained a significance value of 0.002 (Sig. <0.05) then H0 is rejected. This means that people have a significant effect on the decision to choose the students of the Faculty of Economics and Business in the Harapan University Medan

Process Effect on Decision to Choose

Based on Table 4.9 the results of testing the hypothesis the influence of the

Process on the Decision to choose obtained a significance value of 0.004 (Sig. <0.05) then H0 is rejected. This means that the process has a significant effect on the decision to choose the students of the Faculty of Economics and Business in the Harapan University Medan environment.

Effect of Physical Evidence on Choosing Decisions

Based on Table 4.9 the results of the hypothesis testing of the effect of Physical Evidence on the decision to choose obtained a significance value of 0.002 (Sig. <0.05) then H0 is rejected. This means that Physical Evidence has a significant effect on the decision to choose the Students of the Faculty of Economics and Business in the Harapan University Medan environment.

Effect of Reference Groups on Decision to Choose

Based on Table 4.9 the results of testing the hypothesis of the influence of the Referral Group on the decision to choose obtained a significance value of 0.002 (Sig. <0.05) then H0 is rejected. This means that the Reference Group has a significant effect on the decision to choose the Faculty of Economics and Business in the Harapan University Medan environment.

The results of the F statistical test (simultaneous test) on the Marketing Mix (Product, Price, Location, Person, Process, Physical Evidence) and reference group on the decision to choose can be seen in Table 4.10.

Table 4.10 Simultaneous Test (F)

ANOVA ^b						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	438.154	7	62.593	56.409	.000 ^a
	Residual	102.086	92	1.110		
	Total	540.240	99			
a. Predictors: (Constant), Reference Group, Location, Physical Evidence, Process, Price, Person, Product						
b. Dependent Variable: Decision to Choose						

Source: Attachment to SPSS Output

Based on Table 4.10 the results of simultaneous hypothesis testing the influence of Marketing Mix (Product, Price, Location, Person, Process, Physical Evidence) and reference group on the decision to choose obtained a significance value of 0,000 (Sig <0.05) then H0 is

rejected. This means that the Marketing Mix and reference groups simultaneously have a significant effect on the Decision to choose Students of the Faculty of Economics and Business in the Harapan University Medan.

Coefficient of Determination

Test Statistic coefficient of determination in this study the aim is to find out how far the ability of the model in

explaining the variation of the dependent variable. The statistical test of the coefficient of determination can be seen in Table 4.17 below:

Table 4.11 Coefficient of Determination

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.901 ^a	.811	.797	1.05339
a. Predictors: (Constant), Kelompok Referensi, Lokasi, Bukti Fisik, Proses, Harga, Orang, Produk				
b. Dependent Variable: Keputusan Memilih				

Source: Attachment to SPSS Output

The table above shows that the value of R Square is 0.811 or 81.1%, while the adjusted R Square value is 0.797 or 79.7%, which means that the value of R Square is greater than the value of Adjusted R Square percentage of the influence of independent variables (Marketing Mix and reference

group) on The decision to choose is equal to the coefficient of determination or 79.7 %%. While the remaining 90.1% is influenced or explained by other variables not included in this research model. The results of the research hypothesis testing are summarized in Table below:

Table 4.12 Results of Testing Research Hypotheses

No	Hypotheses	Regression Coefficient	Sig.	Conclusion
H ₁	The product has a positive and significant effect on the decision to choose Economics and Business Students in the Harapan University Medan environment.	0,232	0,049	Accepted
H ₂	Price has a positive and significant effect on the decision to choose Economics and Business Students in the Harapan University Medan environment.	0,215	0,023	Accepted
H ₃	The location has a positive and not significant effect on the decision to choose Economics and Business Students in the Harapan University Medan environment	0,073	0,399	Rejected
H ₄	People have a positive and significant influence on the decision to choose Economics and Business Students in the Harapan University Medan environment.	0,263	0,012	Accepted
H ₅	The process has a positive and insignificant effect on the decision to choose Economics and Business Students in the Harapan University Medan environment.	0,090	0,438	Rejected
H ₆	Physical Evidence has a positive and significant effect on the decision to choose Economics and Business Students in the Harapan University Medan environment.	0,276	0,043	Accepted
H ₇	Reference groups have a positive and not significant effect on the decision to choose Economics and Business Students in the Harapan University Medan	0,026	0,666	Rejected
H ₈	Products, Prices, Locations, People, Processes, Physical Sciences and Reference Groups simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on the decision to choose Economics and Business Students in the Harapan University Medan environment.	0,901	0,000	Accepted

Source: 2017 Research Results (Processed)

Table 4.12 shows that the product has a positive and significant effect on the decision to choose, so H1 is accepted. This means that if the Faculty of Economics and Business in Harapan University Medan improves the quality of its products, the decision to choose the Students of the Faculty of Economics and Business will also increase. In line with this, the price also has a positive and significant effect on the decision to choose, so H2 is accepted. This means that with the appropriate prices the Students of the Faculty of Economics and Business will increase their voting decisions within the Harapan University Medan.

Table 4.12 shows that the location has a positive and not significant effect on the decision to vote, so that H3 is rejected. This means that the location of the Faculty of Economics and Business in the Harapan University Medan is less a concern for students in deciding to study at the Faculty of Economics and Business in the Harapan University of Medan. While people have a positive and significant influence on the decision to choose, so that H4 is accepted. This means that if Harapan University Medan increases the understanding of people working at the University, the decision to choose the Students of the

Faculty of Economics and Business will also increase.

Table 4.12 shows that the process has a positive and not significant effect on the decision to vote, so that H5 is rejected. This means that the process at the Harapan University Medan in attracting new students is less a concern for students in deciding to study at the Faculty of Economics and Business in Medan. While physical evidence has a positive and significant effect on the decision to vote, so H6 is accepted. This means that if the Harapan University Medan increases the physical evidence of the University, the decision to choose the Students of the Faculty of Economics and Business will also increase.

Table 4.12 shows that the reference group has a positive and not significant effect on the decision to vote, so that H7 is rejected. This means that the reference group that recommends lectures at Harapan University Medan is less effective so that it has not become a concern for students in deciding to study at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan. While in simulta the product variable, price, location, person, physical form process and reference group simultaneously have a positive and significant influence on the decision to choose, so that H8 is accepted. This means that if the Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University Medan improve the marketing mix and reference group strategies well and effectively, the decision to choose the Students of the Faculty of Economics and Business will also increase.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of hypothesis testing, conclusions that can be drawn from each test hypothesis are as follows:

1. There is a positive and significant effect of the product on the decision to choose students in the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.

2. There is a positive and significant effect of the price on the decision to choose students in the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University Medan.
3. There is a positive and not significant influence from the location on the decision to choose students in the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.
4. There is a positive and significant influence from people on the decision to choose students in the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.
5. There is a positive and insignificant effect of the process on the decision to choose students in the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University Medan.
6. There is a positive and significant influence of the physical form on the decision to choose students in the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University Medan.
7. There is a positive and insignificant influence from the reference group on the decision to choose students in the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.
8. There is a positive and significant influence of the product, price, location, person, process, physical form and reference group simultaneously on the decision to choose students in the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.

Recommendation

The results of the analysis in this study can provide input that can be used by the management of the Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University Medan and also the next researcher. There are several reports that can be used as recommendations from this study:

1. In general, the students feel confident about the marketing mix and reference groups in the Harapan University Medan, but so that the decision to choose students in the Faculty of Economics and Business

Harapan University Medan is increasingly convinced that there are several strategies that must be improved in the location strategy location that is difficult to reach when using public transportation facilities causes students to be less interested in studying at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan. It is expected that the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University Medan can provide facilities to facilitate students in reaching campus locations, for example by providing buses . Then the process strategy, With the existence of a well-integrated process, the community should be able to easily decide to study at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan, and reference groups, which will be expected to the management of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, because it is proven that it has not had a significant effect on the decision to have students. It provides good service and comfort which later can become a reference for students to study at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.

2. Products, prices, people and physical forms owned by the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University Medan in general can be said to be good but, still need improvement in some respects, especially regarding the accreditation of Study Programs, prices lower than competitors, people who more active in introducing the Faculty of Economics and Business Harapan University Medan and the physical form of the Harapan University Medan that must be more attractive so that students can improve their decision to choose to study at the Faculty of Economics and Business, Harapan University, Medan.
3. The value of R-Square (R²) in the marketing mix factor and reference group towards the decision to vote is 79.7%. In other words there are still 20.3% of other variables outside of this research model. For this reason, it is expected that the next researcher can test the research by adding independent variables that have not been discussed in this study such as service, promotion, brand image that can influence student decisions.
4. Further researchers are also advised to use other models besides multiple linear

regression, for example by path analysis (path analysis) and moderating so that the results of the research can be a differentiator of this research and become more varied so that marketing mix strategies, especially in the field of services, can be well developed .

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